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LASU Journal of Management and Social Sciences is a multi-disciplinary journal published by the Lagos State University, Nigeria. Its major aim is to serve as rallying-point for intellectual brainstorming and to contribute towards the attainment of sustainable development in Nigeria by providing a forum for ideas initiated and empirically tested by research experts to be published for the benefit of Policy Makers, Administrators and other functionaries in both the private and public sectors of the Nigerian economy.

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ADVERTISEMENT AND CONSUMER PATRONAGE OF SELECTED BRANDS OF TOOTHPASTE IN ABIA STATE, NIGERIA

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** Victor Monday Dibie

*** Kalu Chisom

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ABSTRACT

The study focused on advertisement and consumer patronage of selected brands of toothpaste in Abia State, Nigeria. A survey research design was used for the study. The population of the study consisted of 445,772 persons derived from three LGAs, each from one Zone of the state, namely, Isikwuato LGA from Bende zone (115,794), Aba North LGA from Aba Zone (106,844) and Umuahia North LGA from Umuahia Zone (223,134). The sample of the study 300 was drawn through Taro Yamane formula and simple random sampling technique was used. Questionnaire was the major instrument for data collection. The data collected were analysed using multiple regression analysis. The result of the findings indicated that effective advertising assists in influencing perceived quality and other perceptions of a product (toothpaste as in this study) thereby leading to increased market share and greater profitability. Advertising was also seen to be important in creating brand awareness, preference, and selection of product or services. Sales promotion and advertisement were significantly influenced by consumers' demographics and buying behaviour respectively while advertisement was also shown to have a strong influence on brand switch. Based on the findings of the study, the researcher recommended that since consumers are open to a variety of brands and conflicting interests, marketers may have to assess the market segment that will appreciate specific promotion techniques in order to get to get maximum response, which will in turn result in increased sales; the primary objective of sales promotion. Also, marketing organizations may have to set up sales promotion departments and units which will be responsible for carrying out market research on the right sales promotion techniques to apply for each market segment.

Keywords: *Advertisement, Consumer Patronage, Promotional Techniques, Sales Promotion and Brand Switch*

INTRODUCTION

Oral care has been a long time way of life considered to be as old as man. From ages, this has been an integral part of man's daily life. Oral care materials like the use of ash and charcoal mixture, chewing sticks etc. were used in past decades but with modernization, these materials have grown obsolete and almost extinct. There is a paradigm shift to the use of toothpastes whose market has considerably grown with a lot of exerting influence. In the

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Nigeria oral care market, such brands as Colgate, Close-up, Darbur, Pepsodent, Macleans, Sensodyne, Anchors, Mymy, and Meswak all exist (Oladele *et al.*, 2015) with a growing demand for them; these all come in different variants, sizes, colours, flavours, and tube shapes. The multiplicity of brands have left consumers with a variety of choices and increased desire for utility maximization. These have created stiffened competition and as such toothpaste producing firms and companies are faced with a herculean task of customers' retention and enforcing brand loyalty. To overcome these, they are constantly devising means to reach their target market and ensure survival through a mix of promotional services such as advertising.

A company cannot make dream to be a well-known brand until they invest in their promotional activities, for which consumer market have been dominating through advertisements (Hussainy *et al.*, 2008). As the primary mission of advertiser is to reach prospective customers and influence their awareness, attitudes and buying behavior. They spend a lot of money to keep individual's interest in their products. They need to understand what makes potential customers behave the way they would like. It also appears that advertising may have the potential to contribute to brand choice among consumers (Latif *et al.*, 2011).

The major aim of advertising is to impact on buying behavior; however, this impact about brand is changed or strengthened frequently in people's memories. Memories about the brand consist of those associations that are related to brand name in consumer mind. These brand cognition influence consideration, evaluation, and finally purchases (Romaniuk and Sharp, 2003). The principal aim of consumer behavior analysis is to explain why consumers act in particular ways under certain circumstances. It tries to determine the factors that influence consumer behavior, especially the economic, social and psychological aspects (Ayanwale *et al.*, 2005).

Advertising is a subset of promotion mix which is one of the 4P's in the marketing mix i.e. product, price, place and promotion. As a promotional strategy, advertising serve as a major tool in creating product awareness in the mind of a potential consumer to take eventual purchase decision. Advertising, sales promotion and public relations are mass-communication tools available to marketers. Advertising through all mediums influence audiences, but television is one of the strongest medium of advertising and due to its mass reach; it can influence not only the individual's attitude, behavior, life style, exposure and in the long run, even the culture of the country (Latif and Abideen, 2011).

The evolution of advertisement dates back to the ancient times. Societies used symbols, and pictorial signs to attract their product users. Over centuries, these elements were used for promotion of products. In the early ages, these were handmade and were produced at limited scale for promotions. Later on, this phenomenon gained strength more intensively for promotional purposes. Today's modern environment, advertisements have become one of the major sources of communication tool between the manufacturer and the user of the products.

Traditional hierarchy-of-effects models of advertising stated that advertising exposure leads to cognitions, such as memory about the advertisement, the brand; which in turn leads to attitudes, i.e. Product liking and attitude toward purchase; which in the end leads to behaviors, like buying the advertised product (Mendelson and Bolls, 2002). As the market is surplus with several products or services, so many companies make similar functional claim; so, it has become extremely difficult for companies to differentiate their products or services based on functional attributes alone. Differentiations based on functional attributes, which are shown in advertisement, are never long lasting as the competitors could copy the same (Hussainy *et al.*, 2008).

Therefore, a consumer is more likely to associate with advertisements of those brands, which have emotional values and messages because positive emotional appeals also provide a strong brand cue and stimulate category-based processing, (Abideen and Latif, 2011), if the categorization process is successful, then the affect and beliefs associated with this category in memory are transferred to the object itself.

Consumers are not only at first confused and disordered in mind, but they also try to categorize the brand association with their existing memory, when thousands of products are faced by them, and they might reposition memories to outline a brand image and perception/concept toward new products. They can categorize latest information into particular brand or product group label and store them accordingly. This procedure is not only associated to consumer's familiarity and information, but also attachment and preference of brand. It is also suggested that consumer can disregard or prevail over the dissonance from brand extension (Abideen and Latif, 2011).

A lot of firms in the industry have embarked on one strategy or the other in order to gain more market share for their products. In an attempt to get more customers to purchase their products, companies have engaged in different innovations so as to make their product compete with that of competitors, the packaging form is one way to gain consumer notice (Berkowitz, 1987).

Furthermore the abundance of scientific literature on this issue do not provide unanimous answer concerning impact of package elements on consumer's buying behavior: diversity of the results in this area depends not only on research models constructed and methods employed, but on the context of the research too. In order to make their advertising campaign even more effective and rewarding, advertisers are trying to analyze various factors which may influence customers' buying behavior e.g. residential area lifestyle, education etc.

The above mentioned issues confirm the necessity to investigate in details the effect of advertisement on the consumption behaviour of toothpaste users in Abia state, Nigeria. In the light of these problematic aspects, the following research questions were asked:

- i. Do promotional techniques influence consumers' patronage of toothpaste brands?
- ii. What is/are the effect (s) of sales promotion on the consumers' demographics with regards to purchase behaviour?
- iii. is there any effect of advertisement attributes on toothpaste consumers' buying behaviour and;
- iv. What impact does advertisement have on brand switch (decision to switch brand for another).

LITERATURE REVIEW

Conceptual Framework

Concept of Advertising and Consumer Behaviour

Researchers have conceptualized migration from various viewpoints ranging from the advertiser to the consumer.

According to Kotler (2000), advertising is any non-personal presentation and promotion of ideas, goods, or services by an identified sponsor. Advertiser includes not only business firms but also museums, charitable organizations and government agencies that direct messages to target public. Advertising can also be defined as any paid non-personal communication about an organization, products, services or ideas by an identified sponsor (Bennet, 2006). Advertising is any paid message presented through various media, such as television, radio, magazine, newspapers or billboards by an identified source.

Scholars such as Sandage and Rotzoll (2002) have argued that advertising is a cost-effective way to disseminate messages, for instance to build brand preference for a product or to educate people about government policies or to avoid consumption of hard drugs. Companies embark upon advertising not only to sell their products, promote their goods, but also to create efficient defense to curtail competitors' moves. Frank (2005) saw advertising with the aim to persuade people to buy. Modern advertising is a product of the twentieth century; however, communication has been a part of the selling process ever since the exchange of goods between people started (Kazimi, 2005). Modern commercial advertising is the persuasive force that aims at changing customers' behaviors. This is important because consumer wants and needs change as their economic positions improve and as they pass through different stages. It is therefore desirable for advertisers to assess the impact of advertisement on their products' performance from time to time (Kotler, 2000).

Shimp (2007) in corroborating Richards and Curran (2002) defined advertising as a paid, mediated form of communication from an identifiable source, designed to persuade the receiver to take some action, now or in the future. A broad variety of rational motives can be used as the source for advertising appeals such as convenience, economy, health, sensory benefits, quality, performance, comfort, reliability, durability, efficiency, efficacy etc.; all of these are to stimulate the consumer to patronize a product (Duncan, 2002).

According to Giles (1974) as cited in Adewale (2004) advertising is a non-personal communication directed at target audience through various media in order to present and promote products, services and ideas. Hancock and Holloway (2002) stated that advertising are those marketing activities other than personal selling, publicity and public relations that stimulate consumer purchasing and dealers effectiveness, such as displays, shows and exhibitions, demonstrations and various non-recurrent selling efforts not in ordinary routine. Wright (2000) defined advertising as a short term incentive to the traders or consumers to induce the purchase of a product. Engel (2000) stated that advertising informs customers about a product and also sells the product.

Advertising, sales promotion and public relations are mass-communication tools available to marketers. As its name suggests, mass communication uses the same message for everyone in an audience. Today, definitions of advertising abound. We might define it as communication process, a marketing process, an economic and social process, a public relations process or information and persuasion process (Arens, 1996). Dunn *et al.* (1978) viewed advertising from its functional perspectives, hence they define it as a paid, non-personal communication through various media by business firms, non-profit organization, and individuals who are in some way identified in the advertising message and who hope to inform or persuade members of a particular audience.

Objectives of Advertising

The advertiser's primary objective is to reach prospective customers and influence their awareness, attitudes and buying behaviour. They spend a lot of money to keep individuals (markets) interested in their products. To succeed, they need to understand what makes potential customers behave the way they do. The advertiser's goal is to get enough relevant market data to develop accurate profiles of buyers to find the common group (and symbols) for communications. This involves the study of consumers' behaviour: the mental and emotional processes and the physical activities of people who purchase and use goods and services to satisfy particular needs and wants (Arens, 1996).

Proctor *et al.* (1982) noted that the principal aim of consumer behaviour analysis is to explain *why consumers act in particular ways under certain circumstances*. This definition does not emphasize the ability of the advertiser to influence the prospective consumer to act exactly the way he wants. It tries to determine the factors that influence consumer behaviour,

especially the economic, social and psychological aspects that can indicate the most favored marketing mix that management should select. Consumer behaviour analysis helps to determine the direction that consumer behaviour is likely to make and to give preferred trends in product development, and attributes of alternatives communication method etc. Consumer behaviours' analyses views the consumer as another variable in the marketing sequence, a variable that cannot be controlled and that will interpret the product or service not only in terms of the physical characteristics, but in the context of this image according to the social and psychological makeup of that individual consumer (or group of Consumers).

Similarly, economic theory has sought to establish relationships between selling prices, sales achieved and consumer's income; however, advertising expenditure is frequently compared with sales. On other occasions, financial accounting principles maybe applied to analyze profit and loss, management ratios, net profit before tax, liquidity and solvency ratios can all be investigated. Under the situations the importance of the consumer's motivations, perceptions, attitudes and beliefs are largely ignored. The consumer is assumed to be "rational" that is, to react in the direction that would be suggested by economic theory and financial principles.

Tellis (2000) opined that advertising is to encourage purchase by temporarily improving the value of a brand. The main objective of advertising is to translate favourable attitudes into actual purchase, improve attitude towards a brand and nurture brand loyalty at all times. Donald (2000) stated that regardless of the exact technique employed, advertising should attempt to accomplish four fundamental tasks:

1. Advertising objectives should relate to overall marketing and should be clearly measurable. This requires that the promotional strategies should adequately define what the promotion wishes to accomplish;
2. Advertising technique should be used to supplement sales and advertising efforts;
3. Advertising like other promotional forms should attract attention among those people they are intended to influence; and
4. Advertising should generally persuade the target audience to place an order i.e. to really close the sale and perhaps assume it has been done. There must be readily recognizable link between the promotion and desirability of buying the particular product. According to Adeleye (1998) advertising has three objectives:
 1. **Sales:** Some firms, especially those involved in direct response can define and measure their advertising objectives in terms of unit or Naira sales or specific sales. Leads and Shultz (1990) contented that setting sales as the advertising objective is the most acceptable way of measuring advertising impact.
 2. **Behavioural effect:** When advertising cannot be defined directly in terms of final sales, some types of behavioural activity by consumers may be used as a measure of the impact of the advertising campaign. For example, some advertisers try to get their target audience to take a specific action short of making a purchase such as requesting for more information, or visiting a retail outlet.
 3. **Communication effect:** Firms do set and measure their advertising objectives in terms of awareness, knowledge, preference, or some other mental effect on the consumer. The observation made by Adeleye (1998) shared the same opinion with Kotler (2000) in which he postulated that most advertisers try to measure the communication effects of an advertisement i.e. its potential effects on awareness, knowledge or preference apart from sales effect. However, it is often apparent that consumer behaviours do not fall neatly into these expected patterns. It is for these

reasons that consumer behaviour analysis is conducted as yet another tool to assess the complexities of marketing operations (Adeolu *et al.*, 2005).

Measuring Advertising Effectiveness

Advertising is designed to create awareness, stimulate loyalty to the company, or create a favourable attitude towards a product. Even though advertising may not directly precipitate a purchase decision, advertising programs must be held accountable. Thus, the business advertiser must be able to measure the result of current advertising in order to improve future advertising and must be able to evaluate the effectiveness of advertising expenditures against expenditures on other elements of marketing strategy (Akanbi and Adeyeye, 2011).

According to Martin *et al* (1988), measuring advertising effectiveness means assessing advertising's impact on what "intervenes" between the stimulus (advertising) and the resulting behaviour (purchase decision). The theory is that advertising can affect awareness, knowledge, and other dimensions that more readily lend themselves to measurement. In essence, the advertiser attempts to gauge advertising's ability to move an individual through the purchase decision process.

It is easier for instance to estimate the effect of a new machine in the factory than it is to predict the impact of higher advertising outlays (Kamber, 2002). Kotler (2000) asserted that advertising effectiveness is predicated upon message content, medium use, product perception and other factors which in varying degree determine its effectiveness.

Good planning and control of advertising depend on measures of advertising effectiveness. However, most measurements of advertising effectiveness deal with specific advertising campaigns. Most of the money is spent by agencies on pretesting ads, and much less is spent on evaluating their effectiveness. Most advertisers try to measure the communication effects of an ad, that is, its potential effect on awareness, knowledge or preference, and on sales efficiency (Kotler, 2000).

Forester (1999) and Russel (1999) posited that advertising sales effect is generally harder to measure than its communication effects. Sales are influenced by many factors such as the product features, price and availability as well as competitor's actions. They argued that the few or more controllable these other factors are, the easier it is to measure effect on sales. Sundarsan (2007) found that the sales impact is easier to measure in direct-marketing or corporate image building advertising.

David and James (1982) observed that companies are generally interested in finding out whether they are spending or under spending on advertising. Researchers try to measure the sales impact through analyzing either historical or experimental data. John and Judy (1996) observed that a growing number of researchers are striving to measure the sales effect of advertising expenditure instead of settling on communication effect measure. Millward Brown international has conducted tracking studies in the United Kingdom for many years to provide information to help advertisers decide whether their advertising is benefiting their brand (Nigel, 1994).

Influencing Consumers' Emotional Response through Advertising

Advertisement is one of the effective tools of integrated marketing communication to emotionally motivate consumers to buy the products. It also has strong linkage with entertainment and the proliferation of media has blurred the distinguishing lines between advertisements and entertainment (Moore, 2004). Advertising is to create brand awareness, preference, and selection of product or services. The most influencing theory in marketing and advertising research is attitude-towards-the-ad. However, the attitude that is formed towards the ad help in influencing consumer's attitudes toward the brand until their purchase

intent (Goldsmith and Lofferty, 2002). Consumer buying behavior is based on the concept and idea that he/she simply decided to purchase a product or service at the spot (Adelaar *et al.* 2003). As the goal of effective advertising is to form positive attitude toward ad and the brand, to increase the number of purchase, then a positive emotional response to an ad may be the best indicator of effective advertising (Goldsmith and Lofferty, 2002). That's why basic aim of advertising to encourage people to buy things and create awareness (Bijmolt *et al.* 1998).

Advertising proliferate the beliefs that possessions are more important and desirable qualities like beauty, achievement, prominence and happiness can be acquired only by material possessions (Latif and Abideen, 2011). For example, a man can be convinced to buy an air conditioner in an arctic region through advertising.

Theoretical Framework

The Marketing Communication Process

The marketing communication process originates from the old mathematical communication theory published by Shannon and Weaver in 1949. This theory was created to show how electrical signals could be transferred from one point to another and came to be introduced as a communication theory within human communication when Weaver thought it also met the demands on how humans affect each other (Barlow, 2002).

This mathematical model has since then been identified as a transmission model of communication and has been adapted widely around the world. During the years, this model has been evolved to form the different process-models for communications (Dwyer, 2005). Models that can be found on the communication process in literature today are all inclined on a base where a sender has to exist to send out a message to a receiver. The sender creates a need/purpose with its communication, chooses a message to send out through the right channel that can lead to a created need among the audience/receiver (Strategic Direction, 2006).

The communication process model is created to show that communication consist of several different elements in constant interaction with each other. There is said to be seven main elements in this process model: sender, message, receiver, feedback, channel, context or setting and noise or interference. This seven are equally important in the process of communication and without one of them, the process will not be complete (Dwyer, 2005). Another very important element in this process is the communication barriers. These occur as a result of misunderstanding or misinterpretation of the message. Being able to recognize these is an important step towards having a successful external marketing communication.

Empirical Framework

Okeji (2008) evaluated effective advertising as an effective marketing tool in Nigeria: Evidence from food and beverages industry. He employed a total sample of fifty members of staff of the Nigerian Bottling Company as respondents to investigate their perception regarding the effectiveness of advertising as a marketing tool in the company. The responses were analyzed using correlation and the Chi-square statistic. The study found that advertising contributes positively to sales of the Nigerian Bottling Company Plc. as depicted by 100% response rate. The weakness of the study lies in its arbitrary drawing of sample size without recourse to any objective criteria. Thus it becomes very difficult and unsafe to generalize based on the findings of the study.

Abiodun (2011) examined the impact of advertising on sales volume of Starcomms Plc. The study used frequency tables, percentages and Chi-square to establish relationship between advertising and sales volume of the company. Despite the attempt made by the study to establish relationship between advertising and sales volume of the company, the study

suffers from a number of weaknesses. The study failed to clearly reveal the impact of advertising on the sales volume of the firm because it utilized primary data that does not adequately capture the impact of relationships. Similarly, the sampling procedure of the study and the absence of validity and reliability test for the research instruments may have affected the data collected and by implication the findings of the study. Lastly, the number of questionnaire copies filled and returned was not adequate by any systematic standard for the test of hypothesis.

Adelaar *et al.* (2003) conducted a study on online compact discs (CDs) shopping behavior of consumer through emotional advertising. Advertising is a non-personal and paid form where ideas, concepts, products or services, and information, are promoted through media (visual, verbal, and text) by an identified sponsor to persuade or influence behavior (Ayanwale *et al.* 2005; Bovee *et al.* 1995).

In a related study, Akanbi and Adeyeye (2011) examined the relationship between advertising and sales volume of Nigerian Bottling Company Plc. between 1999 and 2009. Using the OLS regression technique and t-test on annual time series data of advert costs and sales volume as surrogates; the study found a significant relationship between advertising and sales volume of the company. Despite the fact that the study provided a modest attempt to establish relationship between advertising and sales volume of NBC Plc., it is not completely spared of some limitations. First and foremost, the study failed to establish the stationarity of the time series data used for testing the relationship. Furthermore, given that the study aims at finding out how advert costs can improve sales, the right proxies to employ should have been advert cost and sales in their absolute values. Thus, it is highly unlikely if the results of the study were not affected by these methodological issues.

Mass media and advertising also make available information about consumption and the value of material goods (Abideen *et al.*, 2011). O'Guinn and Faber (1989) explained that once buying behavior is developed, the individual face great difficulty in controlling buying even after its detrimental effects are recognized. Television advertising is a form of advertising in which goods, services, organizations, ideas, etc., are promoted via the medium of television. Through television, advertisers can reach a wide variety of consumers (Abideen *et al.*, 2011).

Furthermore, Akeen (2011) evaluated customer attitude towards internet advertising and online sales using MTN Nigeria as a case study. In the study, a simple random probability sampling technique, simple frequency tables and the Chi-square statistical tools were adopted for data analysis. The finding has shown that there is relationship between availability of uninterruptible power supply and effective internet advertising/online sales.

Over a number of years in the past, many models and constructs have been discussed in the marketing and advertising literature, each having the objective of trying to understand the processes used by consumers to make brand or product evaluations when they are exposed to advertisements (Muehling *et al.*, 1993).

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study employed a survey (cross-sectional study) design. It was aimed at examining the influence of advertising on consumer behaviour for toothpaste in Abia State.

Population of the Study

The population of this study consists of 445,772 persons derived from three LGAs, each from one Zone of the state, namely, Isikwuato LGA from Bende zone (115,794), Aba North LGA from Aba Zone (106,844) and Umuahia North LGA from Umuahia Zone (223,134).

Sample Size

This study adopted the proportional allocation approach as used by Zaur (2001).

Therefore, the sample size for this study is 300

Method of Data Collection

This study made use of both primary and secondary data sources. Primary data were elicited from the respondents with the use of well-structured questionnaire. Data were collected on personal characteristics of the respondents, toothpaste preferences and consumption etc.

Method of Data Analysis

For the purpose of this study, descriptive and inferential statistical tools were employed. Descriptive statistics such as tables, means, frequencies and percentages were used while inferential statistics (multiple regression models) was used to test the hypotheses.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Effect of promotion Techniques on Consumers' Patronage

To examine the effect of promotion techniques on consumers' patronage of toothpaste brands in the study area, the Ordinary Least Square (OLS) method was employed. The Linear form of the model was chosen and the result presented in Table 4.20. Four (4) promotional techniques were selected and regressed against the dependent variable (patronage, proxied by amount spent on a particular brand of toothpaste). The result shows that media jingles, information on toothpaste pack, promotion and use of free samples were all positively correlated to toothpaste patronage at 1%, 1%, 1% and 10% respectively. The R^2 value of 0.585 implies that 58.5% variation in the patronage of various toothpaste brands was accounted for by the promotional techniques employed by the product's manufacturers. Similarly, the F-ratio was statistically significant at 1% indicating that a good fit of the regression line (that is, the regression line is a reflection of the changes of in the independent variable included in the model).

Table 1: OLS Estimates of the Effect of Promotion Techniques on Consumers' Patronage of Toothpaste

Variables	Coefficient	Std. Error	T-values
Constant	561.108	98.212	5.713***
Media jingles	.658	.189	3.500***
Information on pack	.742	.191	3.905***
Promotion	86.878	23.989	3.622***
Free samples	.940	.617	1.524*
F-ratio	4.683***		
Adjusted R^2	.200		
R^2	.585		

Source: Field survey, 2026

The result shows a positive relationship between the use of media jingles and patronage of toothpaste brands implying that the use of this promotional technique influences the decision to purchase toothpaste. Jingles are music played and used to promote a product and when these jingles are well composed, they could be very difficult to resist and by so, people are strongly moved to purchase the product being advertised. However, the major limitation to this technique is the poor habit of listening to radio by most rural people and companies are taking easier and more direct approach to achieve their aim of increasing sales while meeting consumers' needs.

The coefficient of pack information was positively signed and related to consumers' patronage of toothpaste brands. This implies that consumers will patronage toothpaste brands with beautiful packs with important information about the product. For example, toothpaste

brands with information on the comprising ingredients, benefits of using such toothpaste (such as strong gums, long lasting fresh breathe), manufacture and expiry dates, NAFDAC registration number have been generally more patronized than those with scanty information. This is because people are conscious of what they consume and must build trust in the product before consumption.

The coefficient of promotion was also positively signed and correlated to toothpaste patronage indicating that with effective and efficient promotion strategies, patronage will increase. The promotion here refers to all other techniques not stated such as price-off, discounts etc. Consumers are constantly on the look for products that are well-known and promotion is one way to establish a brand as well-known and companies go to any length in ensuring that their products are much competitive in the market.

The variable 'free samples' was positively related to consumers' patronage of toothpaste. This implies that toothpaste manufacturers who adopt the use of free samples in promoting their products are certain to command higher competitive advantage in the market and as well as higher sales. Consumers believe that by giving them free samples, their interest is at heart and they would have spent little or nothing in acquiring the product. This method has been one of the most effective of all promotional techniques and products advertised this way have become household products.

Effect of Sales' Promotion on Consumers' Demographics With Respect To Patronage Rate

To examine the effect of sales promotion on the consumers' demographic features and how they affect the rate of patronage of the product, the binary logistic regression technique was employed. The model gave a Pseudo R^2 of 0.5206 which implies that about 52% of changes in the patronage rate of the consumers as a result of changes in the demographic features of the consumers were induced by sales promotion. The log-likelihood ratio (LR) statistic (19.147) is significant, meaning that the explanatory variables included in the model jointly explained the probability of patronage rate. The result shows that level of education and annual income were positively related to patronage rate at 1% level of significance while sex, age and household size were negative at 5% level of significance respectively. The result is presented in Table 4.2.

Table 2: Sales Promotion Influence on Consumers' Demographics

Variables	Coefficient	Std. error	Z	P > z
Constant	-6.159	2.466	-2.501	0.013**
Sex (1=male, 0=female)	.487	.069	2.052	0.041**
Age (Years)	-.569	.912	-2.270	0.023**
Education (Years)	.338	.950	0.360	0.722
Income (N)	.882	.682	2.760	0.006***
Household size	.306	.681	1.920	0.055*
Log likelihood	19.147753			
Pseudo R^2	0.5206			
LR χ^2	41.59			

Source: Field survey, 2026

The coefficient of education was positively related to the rate of patronage of toothpaste product. This implies that an increase in the level of education acquired will lead to an increase in the use of toothpaste. Education enhances one's understanding of use of certain products. Education makes people flexible and receptive to changes and as such, an educated fellow is not stereo-typed and can be made to accept a new product through sales promotion, thus, influencing patronage rate. The marginal change in patronage rate shows that with a unit increase in educational qualification, toothpaste patronage rate will increase by 0.338 or 33.8%. This finding agrees with Oladele *et al.* (2014) but is in contrast with Vani

et al (2011) which established a negative co-efficient relationship between educational qualification and toothpaste patronage rate.

Income coefficient was positively related to the probability of patronage rate as a result of sale promotion influence. Thus, as income increases, patronage rate is expected to increase. This finding is in contrast with previous findings such as Ekeng *et al* (2012), Lifu (2012) and Oladele *et al.* (2014) who all asserted that income is inversely related to impulse buying. This is not so because with an increase in disposable income, consumers have more idle cash balances at their disposal and could afford making impulse purchases. It is possible that since toothpaste is not a frequently purchased item and not a food item, the probability of impulse buying is usually lower. However, income rise could most probably influence the purchase of more expensive brands.

The gender coefficient was negative. This variable was dummied 1 for male and 0 for female implying that with a positive outcome, males are favoured and vice versa. Therefore, with a negative coefficient, purchase rate is higher among female headed households. This is also because females are more affected by sales promotion given their emotional nature, all things being equal. While Oladele *et al.* (2014) found a positive but insignificant relationship; Rasool *et al* (2012) found a significant relationship. This could have been in the way they structured their dummy.

The coefficient of age was negatively related to the probability of patronage rate implying that as consumers advanced in age, there will be reduction of promotion influence on their toothpaste buying decision. Consequently, a unit increase in age, while holding other variables constant, will result in 36.5% decrease in patronage of toothpaste. This means that as the respondents get older, promotional techniques will be less attractive to influence them to buy toothpaste. Oladele *et al.* (2014), Ekeng *et al* (2012) and Lifu (2012) all had their findings in agreement with this study.

Household size was also negatively correlated with patronage rate implying that any increment in any of household size will lead to reduction of promotion influence on toothpaste buying decisions among the sampled respondents. In Vani *et al* (2011) study, the number of children in the family was established to be insignificant in influencing toothpaste purchase in Bangalore city while Oladele *et al.* (2014) agreed with the finding of this study. Larger households are less responsive to sales promotion since they may not be willing to purchase products that are of no immediate importance. However, their response or attitude to such promotional strategies such as cash discount, free samples and gifts may enhance patronage even with large household sizes since less cost are usually involved but for normal promotion geared towards awareness creation, the case is different.

Effect of Advertisement Attributes on Consumers' Buying Behaviour

To examine the effect of advertisement attributes on consumers' behaviour of toothpaste brands in the study area, the Ordinary Least Square (OLS) method was employed. The Linear form of the model was chosen. Six (6) advertisement attributes were selected and regressed against the dependent variable (buying behaviour measured by the number of repeated purchase of the product). The result shows that the use of billboards, radio, television, print media, promotions and celebrities positively influenced buying behaviour at 5%, 10%, 10%, 10%, 10% and 1% levels of significance respectively. The R^2 value of 0.726 implies that 72.6% variation in the consumer behaviour towards toothpaste brands purchase was accounted for by the advertisement attributes included in the model. Similarly, the F-ratio was statistically significant at 1% indicating that a good fit of the regression line (that is, the regression line is a reflection of the changes of in the independent variable included in the model). The result is presented in Table 4.3.

Table 3: OLS Estimates of the Effect of Advertisement Attributes on Consumers' Buying Behaviour

Variables	Coefficient	Std. Error	T-values
Constant	1.348	.433	3.113 ^{***}
Billboard	.318	.121	2.628 ^{**}
Radio	.334	.201	1.662 [*]
Television	.327	.200	1.635 [*]
Print media	.154	.092	1.674 [*]
Promotions	.171	.090	1.900 [*]
Celebrities	.231	.085	2.718 ^{***}
F-ratio	4.009 ^{***}		
Adjusted R ²	.443		
R ²	.726		

Source: Field survey, 2026

The coefficient of billboard was positively correlated to buying behaviour implying that with the use of billboards in advertising, toothpaste consumers would be propelled to repeat purchase. It has been ascertained that people are moved by what they see and billboards provide that form of advertising. Companies are usually averse to using billboards because of the financial involvement but it has been shown that products advertised using billboards have long-lasting effects in consumers' hearts. The result further shows with an extra billboard located within an area while holding other variables constant, repeat buying will increase by 0.318 or 31.8%.

The use of radio also had a strong effect on consumers' buying behaviour of toothpaste. This entails that the more toothpaste is advertised on radio, purchase increases and could be traced to the effect of the accompanying jingles/music adopted on radio adverts. Toothpaste companies ensure effectiveness in this regards when their adverts are placed at intervals and in the middle of interesting programmes and news time. Furthermore, with an additional placement of radio adverts for toothpaste, repeated purchase (buying behaviour) increases by 0.334 or 33.4%. Similarly, the coefficient of television was also positively related to toothpaste consumers' buying behaviour. Though of similar effect, the use of television is expected to be more effective because of the advantage of sight. Sight helps in retention of what has been received. However, the use of television in advertising is not as efficient as expected because of the low rate of television viewing due to the erratic power supply and inability to acquire television especially for the rural poor.

The use of print-media as adopted by manufacturers in advertising toothpaste was positively related to buying behaviour. Print media include such as newspapers, magazines and other sources written on books/papers with the aim of reaching a target population to ensure purchase of a given product. Provided one can read and write, print media could prove an effective means of advertising toothpaste in the study area. However, this system is not effective given the fact that majority of people in the study area do not have the attitude of reading and so they prefer sources that will appeal to their ears and eyes.

Promotional strategies like discount, price offs, labels etc. were found to be a strong influencing factor for buying behaviour. The use of celebrities was also positively related to consumer behaviour.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Conclusion

The advertiser's primary objective is to reach prospective customers and influence their awareness, attitudes and buying behaviour. This study has shown that effective advertising assists in influencing perceived quality and other perceptions of a product (toothpaste as in this study) thereby leading to increased market share and greater

profitability. Advertising was also seen to be important in creating brand awareness, preference, and selection of product or services. Sales promotion and advertisement were significantly influenced by consumers' demographics and buying behaviour respectively while advertisement was also shown to have a strong influence on brand switch.

Recommendations

Based on the major findings of this study, the following recommendations are submitted:

1. Since consumers are open to a variety of brands and conflicting interests, marketers may have to assess the market segment that will appreciate specific promotion techniques in order to get to get maximum response, which will in turn result in increased sales; the primary objective of sales promotion;
2. Marketing organizations may have to set up sales promotion departments and units which will be responsible for carrying out market research on the right sales promotion techniques to apply for each market segment;
3. The information given to consumers about products must be authenticated and proven true and it must function as specified. This is because consumers are becoming more knowledgeable and informed about what they expect of any consumable product;

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